

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers... (Mafara & Adamu, 2023) Doi: [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.8367630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630)

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers and Students on Online Study during School Closure amidst COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstracts

ICT-based learning is kind of learning that use Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to foster, optimize, enhance and support gaining knowledge. Covid-19 has caused the full transformation to ICT-based learning. This study aimed to investigate the advantages, opportunities and challenges of ICT-BL during the pandemic. Systematic analysis of the qualitative results indicated that possibility of Online learning, saving time and money, communication and motivation tool, usage of social media, sharing and processing the knowledge and improving the quality of education were the highest ranked advantages of the ICT-based learning and remote learning, extra time, adoption of new skills and more technologies and MOOCs in addition to family gathering were the most opportunities while internet accessibility, electricity problems, maintenance of infrastructure, high cost of ICT device and lack of expertise, ability to manage classrooms and plagiarism were the high ranked challenges for both students and lecturers to continue online learning. Developing countries need to develop new strategies and techniques to promote ICT-based learning based on innovation, socio-cultural and socio-economic aspects not only financial support.

Keywords: ICT use, Online learning, School closure, COVID-19

Introduction

ICT applications plays significant role in education in new technological era especially during covid-19 pandemic. Although, applications and practices of ICT-based learning (ICL-BL) are not adopted in developing countries as developed countries, but many of developing countries have been forced to adopt ICT-based learning. Developing countries have adopted ICT as part of educational system over the past two decades of the twenty-one century (Shen & Ho, 2020). However, a very few progresses have been made. Indeed, a small percentage of schools /universities in some developing countries including Indonesia have achieved middle levels of effective use of information and communication technology (Lestari & Prasetyo, 2019) to support and change the teaching and learning process in many areas of study. Others are struggling in the first stage of adopting information and communication technologies related to many problems and challenges such as poverty, conflicts, wars and sociocultural procedures Janssen et. al (2019) that hinder the progress in education in developing world. Implementing ICT in learning process in most of educational institutions in developing countries faces some challenges including little to no computer experience, poorly equipped classrooms, most rural schools are not on the electrical grid, expensive and slow internet connections, most schools with computers are not using them as a medium of instruction and shortage of e-learning materials for students (Kettunen & Sampson, 2019; Hinostroza, 2018). On the other hand, implementing ICT in learning has many benefits such as improving engagement and knowledge retention, encouraging individual's learning and collaboration and learning different skills in flexible time.

According to the report from UNESCO 2020, the pandemic has a devastating impact on global education (Statista, 2020). By May 2020, 95% cent students around the world have been affected by the outbreak of the virus, representing 1.7 billion of the students worldwide, from kindergarten to postgraduate, in more than 200 countries (UN, 2020) where governments around the world ordered closures of schools and universities. Based on this fact, many schools and universities world-wide began to adopt online learning. Adoption of ICT-based learning resulted many advantages, opportunities and challenges and that was the reason to write this paper.

Figure 1. Number of students affected by school closures globally, source: (Statista, 2020)

ICT- based learning have many advantages and components such as quality of content, supporting learning system, ability of such system to interactive, ease of use and educational evaluation (Binyamin, Rutter, & and S. Smith, 2019). Besides, advantages could be different modes based on the type of learning such as availability in time and place, equity, enhancing collaboration between students and educators, direct access to different resources, ability to enhance service of education dimensions globally and ability to determine the progress rate in educational courses (Talebian, et al, 2014). Use of ICT has positive impact on learning in high schools and ICT factors such as infrastructure, devices, techniques, methods and applications have more affective influence to learning in undergraduate and graduate levels (Al-Ansi, et al., 2019). In the other hand, penetration of electronic devices in learning such as laptops, cell-phones and tablets and availability of these devices for students facilitated the ability of learning. Some of studies stated that number of mobile devices are more than the people in the globe were reached more than 7.9 billion devices. This enables usage of m-learning effectively and offers many of opportunities in learning anywhere anytime regardless some limitations in use of mobile device as learning tool (Criollo-C, Luján-Mora, & A. Jaramillo-Alcázar, 2018). Advantages of ICT usage in learning include control of the content, control the approaches of presentation, creativity and modernity, ability to give feedback anytime and Adaptability (Padurean, 2009).

Regardless the negative impact of Covid-19 in our life today, ICT-Based learning has many opportunities during this pandemic including saving more time and expenses, adoption more technologies to learning, learning new skills and availability of learning materials online all the time in addition to the gathering with family while studying/teaching. Different previous studies discussed the opportunities of ICT-Based learning in enhancing the abilities and competencies of students/educators and facilitating learning process (Al Ansi & Al-Ansi, 2020). The use of social networking tools to enhance collaborative learning activities is seen as an effective way for students to experience a sense of ownership of the learning process. (Kurtz, 2014), and guide the student to discuss problems with their classmates. Other studies discussed the importance of collaborative learning role in saving time of students and educators in sending emails, saving, revising and editing materials and other activities which leads to improve their productivity (Huang, 2017). In another hand, social media plays an important role in ICT-based learning at the pandemic time and social distancing. Using of social media and sharing various information in the same platforms would significantly increase students' understanding of complex subject (Erturk, 2016) and able them to post and share their ideas. In addition, teleconferencing applications became the main tool for conducting online classes such as zoom and google teams. Besides, a chatting is a useful approach to mitigate some problems students may be facing when they learn a specific topic. This is due to saving these chatting and students have the ability to read and review anytime they need (Subramani, 2015).

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On the other hand, ICT-based learning in developing countries faces many challenges (Garad & Al-Ansi, 2021). Some of these challenges are about the speed, coverage and cost of internet, electricity problems, high cost of infrastructure, managing and organizing classrooms, maintenance of hardware and software, lack of expertise and sometimes plagiarism. One Study by Çakici (2016) mentioned some problems related to using ICT in classrooms such as inability to use software and hardware of ICT, shortage of technical support, no enough time to use ICT, some difficulties related to access resources, restriction of content and insufficient resources Technology. Another study by Manda and Dhaou (2019) investigated the challenges in the 4th industrial revolution which included potential job loses, skill challenges, Infrastructure challenges, security and privacy. In fact, challenges of ICT-based learning differ among nations. Developed countries experience social challenges such as loss of jobs, disqualified HR, new kinds of stress and some problems related to increasing insecurity in social system (European Parliament, 2016) in addition to Changing business models, data issues, legal issues of liability and intellectual property, and mismatch of standards and skills (Dregger, 2016) while developing countries are more concern about infrastructure, advances in technology and manufacturing techniques, Low e-readiness levels, lack of digital connectivity, skills, knowledge, and innovation (Manda & Backhouse, 2016).

Different research has investigated the role of ICT in education, in addition to exploring benefits and challenges or ICT-based learning and comparing technologies development and implementations in developing and developed countries. This research is unique due to current condition of ICT-based learning. ICT-based learning became the only learning tool because of Covid-19 pandemic. Online learning depends on ICT applications and techniques (Al Ansi A. M., 2017). Many governments in developing countries invested in infrastructure of online learning during past few years where some universities were conducting some classes online through LMS of university. Covid-19 has caused many serious problems to our health system (Al-Ansi, 2021), economy and learning system as well. It is important to mention that adoption and implementation of ICT in education in developed countries are more effective and the problem that educational systems has or policies' makers face are not the same as in developing world. So, investigating the real problems related to ICT-based learning systems in developing countries after the total transforming of learning to be online is what makes this study significant.

This research aims to investigate the opportunities, challenges and advantages of using ICT in learning as solution to face outbreak of the virus worldwide. To get this aim, the following question is raising: what are the advantages, opportunities and challenges of ICT-based learning in developing countries such as Indonesia during the Covid-19 pandemic? Although many developing countries have promoted such technologies effectively since time ago but these countries have not adopted technologies in education as developed countries. To answer this question, direct interviews with students, lecturers, administrative staff and ICT specialist in Islamic schools, Malang city- Indonesia were conducted to explain the advantages, opportunities and challenges of ICT-based learning process in their schools.

According to Stewart et al. (2011), online learning refers to a system of learning where the students learn virtually through the use of the Internet. Dhawan (2020) defines online education as the ability of learners to use devices connected to a network, offering them the possibility to learn with any means, in any rhythm, anytime, and from anywhere. In another piece of research, Singh & Thurman (2019) refer to online learning as "learning experiences in synchronous or asynchronous environments using different devices (e.g., mobile phones, laptops, etc.) with internet access. In these environments, Students can be anywhere (independent) to learn and interact with instructors and other students."

Rapantar et al. (2020) define online learning as internet-enabled learning, which includes collaboration between experts, content creators, a networked community of learners, management of learning experiences, and content delivery. In his research, Kundu (2018) defines online learning as the delivery of course materials via electronic methods such as CDs, television, video or audio tape, satellite broadcast, extranets, intranets, and the internet. Combining these definitions, online learning can be referred to as the internet-based delivery of course content to learners through the use of internet-enabled devices such as laptops and phones. Online learning has been accelerated by fast internet development and globalization, making many institutions of higher learning start to focus on online learning. Mart (2017) says that institutions all over the world have been trying to deviate their spending towards infrastructural development to have distance learning in place as the next best alternative to the traditional classroom teaching method. For its implementation to succeed, online education has to be acceptable to all the stakeholders, or at least a majority of them, such as students, teachers, administrators, parents, and the education ministries. In their study, Shearer et al. (2020), while examining the student's perception of and motivation towards online education, noted that curriculum developers and policymakers should understand the students' limitless perspectives so that they can offer student-centric instructional techniques while increasing students' satisfaction and engagement.

While the developed world has embraced online learning to a greater extent, developing countries have yet to provide schools with relevant infrastructural development to integrate virtual learning as a supplement to face-to-face learning. The gap

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in access to ICT between the rich and the poor in developing countries is quite wide (Venkatesh and Sykes, 2013). In their research, Srivastava and Shainesh (2015) found out that the set-up of the societies in these countries is grounded on a compound geographical spread and socioeconomic levels where most of the people lack access to basics such as education and healthcare, which makes access to ICT less of a priority. This means that stopping physical learning abruptly to introduce online learning from home had a big effect on the poor. Similarly, considering gender-based differences, females are more affected than their male counterparts, which, according to Cutter (2017), could have placed them among the have-nots considering that at home, they are required to participate in feminine gender roles such as caregiving, cleaning, and cooking. In another study, there were four major factors that should be considered while implementing online learning and that influence its acceptance among the various stakeholders. The first factor is accessibility.

According to Park (2009), online learning accessibility refers to the level of ease with which students in an institution can receive and use the school's online learning system as an organizational factor. He says that to ensure high rates of acceptance among students, schools must ensure that internet accessibility is high enough, so the priority should be to provide students with access to computers and internet connectivity. The next factor is appropriateness, which refers to the fitness of online learning for a student's needs. d'Antoni (2002) says that any e-learning strategy that a school adopts should be best-fit to the needs of a student, depending on their academic level and other needs at the time of its implementation. In their study of open educational resources and open content, Stewart et al. (2011) say that comprehensive online learning for both synchronous and asynchronous communication modes make sure that the implemented strategy is appropriate for all learners. Synchronous teacher-learner and learner-learner communication is enhanced by chat techniques such as message boards and bulletin boards. On the other hand, asynchronous communication is enhanced by the use of less time-sensitive platforms such as emails. To formulate the most appropriate strategy, a school must be able to overcome barriers related to access such as electricity, internet connectivity, and infrastructural redundancy (Laskaris et al., 2017).

Thirdly, schools should consider accreditation of the adopted strategies. Different strategies are guided by the geographical location of a school; for instance, a school's country of origin determines the ease of implementation. Finally, affordability should be considered any time there is an online learning implementation, which is also influenced by the specific location of a school. With these factors in mind, researchers show that online learning implementation in institutions of higher learning should be regarded as an important educational reform.

The above four factors show that effective and efficient implementation calls for huge attention and care to achieve success. In a study looking into the factors that lead to acceptance of ICT in the classroom, Lawrence & Tar (2018) found that successful adoption of online learning requires that teachers and school heads become part of the decision-making process. Their findings were in line with those of Baydas & Goktas (2016) and Mirzajani et al. (2016), who believe that support from senior management plays a significant role during the implementation process. Similarly, in their review, Akkara and Mallampalli (2020) stated that e-learning cannot happen in a vacuum as it needs two of the most important pillars: internet connectivity and the existence of relevant infrastructure. Shehab and Khalifa (2021) carried out a study in Kurdistan to determine the challenges student nurses were facing while studying online. In interviews with 25 students and educators, the researchers found out that Kurdistan faces immense problems, which require that the region invest heavily to boost its infrastructure to allow for the successful implementation of e-learning systems, as the public universities in the region rely on funding from the KRG. Due to these issues, researchers have identified that some schools have opted for blended learning, which requires less capital for implementation (Rassul & Wali, 2020; Shabila et al., 2021).

There are some difficulties felt in the implementation of the change process in the education system that has arisen after the COVID-19 crisis; these difficulties are related to the novel perspectives of online education and their technological complexities. Earlier in this pandemic, online education was considered the education provided by open universities in India. But in the COVID-19-induced time, online teaching and learning became a massive challenge to deal with, and stakeholders are not potentially fit to adjust to the sudden educational change as they are not technologically competent to embrace the current situation. Therefore, for the successful implementation of educational change,

Fig. 2 describes how to decide on the implementation process of online teaching and learning.

The journey begins with the collective vision of UGC and MHRD (supra-system), universities and Colleges (system), and different academic departments (sub-system) in favor of implementing online teaching and learning in the education system. In the face of COVID-19, the shared vision of education system realized that during the pandemic period, teachers and students are motivated to adapt online teaching- learning platforms in fulfilling the current educational needs. Everyone, either teachers or students, was friendly and skilled in using social media apps such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram, which turned into smooth facilitation of using online educational platforms such as Zoom, Cisco WebEx, Google Meet, etc. as a sign of positive transfer of learning. Also, there are some useful educational apps such as Office 365, Google Classroom, and much more user-friendly videoconferencing apps that can be downloaded free of charge and are easy to use (FutureLearn, 2020), so to some extent, it seems that there is no reason to get into a panic to get new technology all of a sudden as some of the apps are already embedded in our HEIs. The majority of stakeholders possessed smartphones, and only a considerable number had laptops. These are the needed resources to implement online teaching and learning.

Mizoram University has an ICT center and LMS that help in seamless monitoring of online teaching and learning modes. The central and State governments unanimously agreed upon implementing online education across the country, keeping in mind the need of the hour. Various national, state, and university-level teachers' and students' associations half-heartedly and hesitatingly supported the vision of online teaching-learning modes with mixed bags of opinion as a result of curiosity to trial new technology and the new mode of the teaching-learning process in the education system; it is due to the lack of preparedness, orientation, and incentives of stakeholders in using the online mode of teaching.

The action plan was prepared keeping in view our readiness for online teaching mode, our drive for change in this pandemic, and the availability of resources for implementing online teaching mode. To go with the action plan, teachers prepared and trained themselves independently to become accustomed to the technology required for using online teaching modes. At the university level, system administrators and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) experts provided necessary assistance to stakeholders and managed the change process. However, while many pieces of research have been conducted on online teaching and learning and its effectiveness, no such studies were conducted during the COVID-19 lockdown period. Hence, the researcher is insightfully interested in doing this study with the following objectives:

Just like their teachers, students also had challenges adjusting to online learning from traditional class-based learning. In the study of barriers to online learning in the time of COVID-19, Ronnie et al. (2020) discovered that students found it difficult to adjust to online learning styles due to having to perform responsibilities at home and poor communication between them and lectures. Students were generally not prepared for online learning. While it was found that social issues and lecturer issues affect students' intentions to study online, access to online learning platforms was a demonstrable major challenge for many students (Aboagye et al., 2020; Chung, 2020; Rapanta et al., 2020).

In particular, technical issues may occur in the middle of online learning, yet most students do not have access to technical support and advanced technologies that facilitate online learning (O'Keefe, 2020). Access to digital learning devices such as laptops and tablets and access to data for internet connections were found to be barriers to online learning for some students (Adnan & Anwar, 2020; Dhawan, 2020; Moawad, 2020). Lack of access to online learning systems is common among students from poor families living in underdeveloped communities. The study that was conducted in West Bengal, India, shows that 30.6% of students studied through reading textbooks by themselves and did not participate in e-learning, mainly due to a

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lack of access to online learning platforms (Kapasias et al., 2020). As also understood by Dawadi et al. (2020), access to online learning for some students in these difficult times is a major problem for the higher education sector as it increases the already existing inequalities among its citizens in terms of their socio-economic status and education or literacy. While some students are dissatisfied with the existing online teaching platforms (Chen et al., 2020), others have more serious challenges to overcome, such as those concerning access to online learning platforms (Ronnie et al., 2020).

Online teaching and learning require a fast and reliable internet connection. Therefore, the shift from traditional face-to-face learning to online learning meant that students and academics had to stay connected to the internet. However, under some circumstances, this may be impossible; hence, teaching and learning would be affected. Challenges with connectivity were highlighted as the leading factor undermining e-learning and e-teaching during lockdown as a result of Covid-19 pandemic outbreak (Aboagye et al., 2020; Bao, 2020; Berezina et al., 2020; Dawadi, 2020; Jena, 2020). In their study of barriers to online learning, Ronnie et al. (2020) found the availability of a fast and reliable internet connection to be a greater concern than either device ownership or technical aptitude. The critical challenge of a reliable internet connection for online learning was also reported in the literature (Mamun et al., 2020; Naciri, 2020) as the main cause of non-participation in online learning by the majority of students. This drawback for online learning, according to Demuyakor (2020), was attributed to a lack of internet data among Ghanaian international students in China. The unavailability of suitable hardware and software to access online learning was also identified as a barrier by some students (Crawford et al., 2020).

In an attempt to ensure that all students have equal access to online learning, Student Representative Councils (SRCs) in various universities demanded the provision of digital learning devices (smartphones, tablets, and laptops) and internet data to all students (Kwabena & Boateng, 2020). However, some students could not access online tools despite having digital learning devices and internet data because of a poor network at home (Aboagye et al., 2020; Rose, 2020; Wargadinata et al., 2020). The poor network problem is particularly common in developing countries where ICT and telecommunications systems are not properly developed (Aboagye et al., 2020). Correspondingly, Chang and Fang (2020) discovered that 60%–70% of teachers agree that "network speed and stability are poor", leading to challenges with accessing online learning tools. This literature evidence suggests that reliable network infrastructure, availability of internet data, and availability of digital learning devices such as smart phones, tablets, and laptops to students are important to ensure smooth online teaching and learning.

The lack of physical learning space and environment also presented itself as a challenge for some students learning online during lockdown. In most poor households, students do not have a private room where they can peacefully study without disturbance (Ronnie et al., 2020). Learning from home therefore becomes difficult for this disadvantaged group of students. The research conducted by Demuyakor (2020) shows that some students have to rush to the toilets to answer calls from their professors or to turn off video feeds because of the noisy background. Similarly, Kapasias et al. (2020) found that, of 232 students, 103 (44.4%) had no separate reading room for the study. Without a conducive learning environment, students are unable to concentrate on their schoolwork, and study productivity is reduced as a result (Chang & Fang, 2020). As argued by Daniel (2020), it is therefore necessary that institutions and educational systems consider the concerns of students whose parents are unsupportive and whose home environments are not conducive to study. The shift to online education during COVID-19 overlooked this reality of an unconducive learning environment, which negatively affects learning outcomes.

The mental health issues associated with COVID-19 and the sudden shift from class-based to online learning are also demonstrable in the literature. Such issues include stress, anxiety, and depression, which occur due to a sudden change in one's lifestyle and uncertainty about the future (Rajkumar, 2020; Ronnie et al., 2020; Rossi et al., 2020; Tandon, 2020; Xiong et al., 2020). Learning loss and drop-out rates, among other harder-to-quantify factors due to COVID-19, cause social and emotional disruption for the general public and worse for students (Dorn, 2020). In addition, students whose family income or livelihood strategy was impacted by COVID-19 and its regulations were found likely to suffer from stress, anxiety, and depression, which in turn affect motivation to engage in online learning (Cao et al., 2020; Husky et al., 2020; Son et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2020; Zolotov et al., 2020). While COVID-19 created fear and other mental health issues among Israeli university students, Zolotov et al. (2020) further discovered that students who were psychologically affected turned to substance use in order to cope. This coping mechanism during these difficult times has a negative impact on learning. Among Chinese students, 24.9% have experienced anxiety because of this COVID-19 outbreak (Pragholapati, 2020). Anxiety was often associated with having a relative or acquaintance who is infected with COVID-19 (Pragholapati, 2020).

There is limited research evidence on the impact of COVID-19 on students' academic performance. This is probably due to the lack of data that measures academic outcomes during the COVID-19 period. However, it is expected that as academic results become available, more research will be conducted in this area. Gonzalez et al. (2020) studied the academic performance of students before and after COVID-19 confinement. Their study results show that students achieved significant improvements

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in their scores even in tests that were performed in an online format in previous years (Gonzalez et al., 2020). Moreover, this improvement is only significant when comparing data after the COVID-19 confinement (i.e., there are no significant differences in on-line tests that were performed before the confinement) (Gonzalez et al., 2020). Therefore, these findings reveal that the new assessment process cannot be the reason for the improvement in students' performance because the learners also achieved better scores when the format of the assessment did not change (Gonzalez et al., 2020). Although Gonzalez et al.'s study did not find the effect of COVID-19 confinement on students' academic performance, it is expected the COVID-19 outbreak will not only cause poor performance among students but also increase the dropout rate (Dorn et al., 2020).

While COVID-19 has created a lot of problems for the higher education sector, it has been recognized that this pandemic has, on the positive side, created opportunities. Such opportunities involve new approaches and tools for learning online and capacity development. For instance, lockdown implemented as a result of COVID-19 pushed universities that previously used traditional teaching methods into the digital world (Ratten, 2020). This means universities must develop innovative ways to deliver teaching without compromising quality (Ratten, 2020).

Also, new challenges associated with online teaching and learning will create a space for innovative thinking and innovative solutions within the sector (Bryson & Andres, 2020). It is also argued that due to online teaching and learning, both students and teaching staff will further develop their online communication and interpersonal skills through regular exposure to online platforms (Beech & Anseel, 2020). The COVID-19 outbreak also presented opportunities for new research in a new area with the increased use of digital data collection methods and a wider exposure to the virtual dissemination of research results. This provided researchers and academics with new experiences in the digital world necessary for their capacity development (Gardner, 2020; Shahzad et al., 2020; Zhu & Liu, 2020). Therefore, not all is bad about COVID-19; however, challenges and problems far exceed opportunities.

One of the theories that guided the current study is Classical Liberal Theory of Equal Opportunities. According to Von Mises (2012), liberalism is an aspect in which equality and individual liberty are considered the most important objectives by emphasizing equality and individual rights. Liberal theories advocate the provision of basic rights for everyone while seeking to avoid favoritism or unfairness. Therefore, the classical liberal theory of equal opportunities holds that an individual matters most and that in any society, an individual must be allowed to live the best life in their own unique way. As such, it is clear that society must take deliberate steps to ensure all individuals receive equal opportunities in any societal realm. In the current study, this theory will be used to elucidate the need for providing learners with equal opportunities despite their coming from different socioeconomic backgrounds. The pandemic has widened economic inequality in the region, which could limit access to education.

The equivalence theory holds that for distance learning to be considered a success, it must provide learning experiences for every student, either locally or distantly. The model states that distance learning is not the same as physical learning, but the two approaches are equivalent (Lapsley et al., 2008). This means that the term equivalency should not be confused with mean equal, but it is a situation in which learning experiences that students receive are considered to give them similar experiences for similar outcomes. However, the main emphasis of the theory is not to expect that every student will be taught or learn in a similar manner (Garratt-Reed et al., 2016). According to Goldie, J. G. S. (2016), connectivism is, to a certain degree, a new theory of Learning suggests that learners need to combine general manners, theories, and thoughts in a useful manner. The theory emphasizes that technology is a key part of the learning process and that persistent connectedness provides people with opportunities to make choices about their learning. The theory states that some of the digital technology features, such as web browsers and search engines, are significant tools that help in online learning implementation. As such, education, being an important aspect of people's lives, is a subject of technology. As Strong & Hutchins (2009) state, learning only happens within ever-changing networks, only after information sources and specialized nodes are connected, and can occur in non-human appliances. In online education, learning happens when various stakeholders interact; an example is the interaction between students and teachers. For this reason, this theory was selected.

Researchers have agreed on the fact that the technology acceptance model (TAM) has been the most influential of all the theories explaining the acceptance of digital transformation. The theory illustrates and describes how people in different societal realms come to accept and widely use a given technology. The actual use of a system is the result of how people use the technology. People are forced by behavioral intention (BI) to embrace technology. But BI is affected by attitude, which is the general impression of the technology. One of the factors that influence acceptance is Perceived usefulness, which has to do with how the users view the technology in question. To accept a given technology, a user must perceive it as useful in their lives, and in this case, the general education Another factor that users consider is ease-of-use, which is defined as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free from effort (Al-Marroof & Al-Emran, 2018). The

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hindrances are removed only if the user thinks that the technology in question is easy to use. This theory will be useful for the current study in explaining why there could have been resistance during the initial stages of the implementation of online learning in Nigeria.

The COVID-19 pandemic presented a demand for online education in a manner that the Ahmadu Bello University and Zaria institutions of higher learning could not keep up with. In a situation where such a demand is experienced, abrupt transitioning could prove impossible, particularly in regions where the resources needed are not readily available. Teachers were not well-versed in the art of distance learning and ensuring that the syllabus was completed on time. Administrators may also need vast training on how to manage teams remotely and have all tasks completed on time. On their side, the parents and society may not accept the instant transition, and they may not be well-versed in guidelines to help their children cope.

Finally, resistance from students could hinder any government efforts to integrate virtual learning methods. With the difficulty that the pandemic presents in the region and beyond and the possible impacts that could be experienced from future pandemics, it is clear that Kurdistan's ability to quickly leverage the available technology, mobilize stakeholders to devise relevant emergency mechanisms to adapt to any new norms and offer the pertinent infrastructural adjustments will determine the continuation of learning in all schools. The impacts of COVID-19 on the education sector have been felt in all countries globally, including Iraq and Kurdistan. The reason is that there was an abrupt disruption of pedagogical processes across all the learning institutions, both K–12 and institutions of higher learning alike. The most affected students are the grade 12 students, who were expecting their national exams at the end of the year. Although they were allowed to attend school normally while others were learning from home, they were psychologically affected, which could greatly impact their test results in this crucial season of their lives.

The disparity in home-based learning poses a huge problem to the acquisition of online learning programs. The inequality is primarily presented by a difference in the socio-economic aspects of the Zaria community, which has been a major issue for a long time. The socioeconomic status of a family affected how well a student received online classes. Those living in impoverished conditions do not have the relevant resources, locking them out of accessing the learning materials shared remotely. This explains the resistance that the adoption of online learning faced from parents whose students studied in public schools, as their situations are already dire. According to Ali et al. (2021), a student's or parent's choice of school in Zaria is heavily influenced by their socio-economic status. Therefore, those living in poor conditions have limited abilities to navigate the disrupted educational landscape in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Many researchers have tried to cover the critical issues that affect the successful implementation of e-learning strategies in developed, developing, and undeveloped countries. A vast number of studies have also been carried out on the challenges that came as a result of the abrupt implementation of e-learning in the wake of COVID-19. The only information available is in news articles and articles from other countries, especially the developed world. News is not scientific and, therefore, may not be used as a source of information during policy recommendations. On the other hand, the literature from Western nations cannot be used since the technological environment and socio-economic factors in the West and Kurdistan differ immensely. Some issues experienced in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, such as unreliable power supply in remote areas, slow telecommunications infrastructure development, and low bandwidth, may not be experienced in other countries, while they might be extreme in others. Thus, a successful transition from traditional methods of learning towards a technology-based education system needs documented scientific evidence from research like the current one. Understanding the challenges towards a successful integration of e-learning as an emergency option. Therefore, the current paper presents the findings from a study investigating the challenges that hindered the successful implementation of online learning in Nigerian public universities when schools were massively closed during the COVID-19 era. The research included the gathering of data from various officials as major stakeholders in various public universities in an interview to present their perceptions on the matter.

Objectives of Study

The objective of the study was to “Examine the challenges faced by teachers and students in adapting to the online teaching and learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic”.

Research Question

What are the challenges faced by teachers and students in adapting to the online teaching and learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic?

Methodology

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers... (Mafara & Adamu, 2023) Doi: [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.8367630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630)

This study employed survey research in order to assess the respondent’s feelings concerning the issues online education has faced since the start of the pandemic. The population of the study comprises of lecturers and students of tertiary institutions in Northwest Nigeria. The sample consists of 160 participants drawn from among lecturers and students in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The sampling approach used for the current research was convenience-type non-probability sampling. Here, the researcher draws a sample from a group of people who are easy to contact or reach. The reason for choosing non-probability sampling and not randomization is because some of the education experts have busy schedules and it would take a long time to book an appointment with them. Due to the time constraint of the research, convenience sampling was the best alternative for the current research. The researcher chooses groups based on their capacity to produce categories (variables) and category attributes and connects them with their qualities. The researcher selected lecturers, ICT technical staff lecturers, and students who had enough knowledge of the online teaching sector to participate in the study. The sample was 65% male and 35% female. One of them is a professor, an associate professor for high information and communication technology staff, senior lecturers, junior lecturers, and students of all types for the province. Looking at their educational attainments, 7.1% of them were Bachelor’s holders, 21.4% were master’s holders, and the remaining 71.4% were Ph.D. holders. The oldest was 66 years old, and the youngest was 36. The researchers distributed one hundred and sixty (160) copies of questionnaires to both lecturers and students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and one hundred and fifty (150) copies of the questionnaire were returned duly completed, representing 96% turn-over. The main reason for the high response was the commitment of the research assistants to ensuring that all distributed questionnaires were collected.

The researchers adopted a quantitative approach using mean and standard deviation to allow for a deeper and broader understanding of the topic in question. The researcher chose to use semi-structured interviews to collect data from the participants. One advantage of this method is that the researcher formulates questions prior to the meeting so that the conversation can be smooth and have the direction to avoid loss of focus. Besides, participants could respond to the open-ended questions in the best possible way to provide in-depth data. To equally get answers from the participants, the researcher asked the same questions to all of them. Lindlof (1995) argues that "by asking the same questions of all participants in roughly the same order, the researcher minimizes interviewer effects and achieves greater efficiency of information gathering".

Results

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Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of responses on challenges in adapting to online learning amidst COVID-19

Statement of Assessment	Mean	Std. Dev	Frequency	%	Decision
Teachers, ICTs, and students faced challenges in adapting to the online teaching-learning process during the Covid-19 pandemic.	2.05	0.99	150	100%	Disagree

The mean score of 2.05 indicates that respondents disagreed with the statement that teachers, ICT professionals, and students easily adapted to the online teaching and learning process. This finding highlights the difficulties faced by these stakeholders in adjusting to the new virtual learning environment. The challenges might include technological issues, limited access to resources, and the need for training and support. Addressing these challenges through targeted interventions and professional development programs can improve the effectiveness of online teaching and learning. The respondents disagreed that teachers, ICT staff, and students faced challenges in adapting to the online teaching-learning process. This implies that there is a consensus among the participants that challenges were encountered during the transition to online education.

Discussion of Findings

This discussion provides insights into the perceptions and experiences of teachers, ICT staff, and students regarding various aspects of online teaching and learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. The disagreements and undecided responses suggest areas of concern and potential areas for improvement in terms of resources, training, support, student participation, and technical management. Based on the analysis of the data, several trends and patterns emerge. The findings indicate that there were generally negative perceptions and challenges associated with online teaching and learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. Respondents expressed disagreement or uncertainty regarding various aspects, such as the effectiveness of different teaching modes, perceptions of teachers and students, adaptation challenges, and government implementation challenges.

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Respondents disagreed that their schools had constant internet connectivity, indicating potential issues with access to stable internet connections. Additionally, there was disagreement regarding the availability of resources for effectively implementing online teaching programs. These findings suggest that improvements in internet infrastructure and resource allocation are necessary to support successful online learning experiences. Respondents expressed disagreement regarding teachers' allocation of periods per week, their effectiveness in enlightening students about the importance of participation, and their attitudes towards students during online learning. These findings suggest a potential need for enhancing teacher-student interaction and engagement strategies in the online learning environment. Respondents generally agreed that the participation of every student is crucial for the success of effective online lessons/learning. This finding emphasizes the significance of fostering active engagement and involvement of students in online learning activities. While respondents disagreed about the impact of students' platform initiatives and the support provided by executive management for online teaching and learning, they were undecided about whether teachers performed necessary monitoring and data backups or if teachers and ICT staff regularly updated systems and security measures. These findings suggest a need for effective management practices, administrative support, and regular system maintenance to enhance the online teaching and learning experience. Respondents disagreed with the statement that ICT staff-regulated learning activities are more effective than teachers-regulated online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. This finding suggests that there might be a perception among respondents that teachers play a more significant role in facilitating online learning compared to ICT staff.

The analysis highlights the need for addressing concerns related to the effectiveness of ICT staff, guidance and support for students, positive attitudes of teachers and ICT staff, executive management support, regular updates, and security measures. These areas can be further explored and targeted for improvement to enhance the overall online teaching and learning experience during school closures and the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, the analysis of the data indicates several areas of concern and opportunities for improvement in the context of home-based learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. The findings highlight the need for addressing challenges related to internet connectivity, resource availability, ICT training, teacher-student interaction, student participation, and effective management and support. By addressing these areas, educational institutions can enhance the quality and effectiveness of online teaching and learning experiences.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the COVID-19 pandemic presented various challenges and uncertainties in the implementation of online teaching and learning. The perceptions and experiences of teachers, students, and ICT staff differed, indicating the need for further research and collaboration to improve online education practices.

Recommendations:

1. Enhance internet connectivity and access to technology resources to overcome the challenges of ICTs application during home-based online learning.
2. Foster collaboration between education stakeholders to develop strategies for effective online teaching and learning.
3. Continuously update and improve online teaching practices based on feedback and lessons learned during the pandemic.

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